

Citations as Filters in Academic Literature Search

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Abstract

Relevance evaluation is a nuanced, context-dependent process that integrates multiple factors, including topicality, novelty and utility. In academic contexts, citation counts have emerged as a critical bibliometric indicator, often serving as proxies for research influence and quality. This study investigates how citation counts are utilized in relevance evaluation by users of academic search engines. Using a within-subject experimental design, participants interacted with manipulated search engine results pages containing citation counts, altmetric scores or no indicators. Analysis of 50 participants' behavior revealed two main functions of citation counts: as positive filters during early search stages to identify highly cited articles, and as negative filters at later stages to exclude poorly cited works. Participants contextualized citation counts only infrequently with other relevance properties, such as publication date, title and journal. In these rare cases, they demonstrated quite clear expectations on citation patterns. However, participants mostly relied solely on raw numbers. These findings highlight the utility of citation counts for relevance evaluation while also revealing the risk of oversimplified assessments when context is overlooked. This study contributes to understanding the complex interplay between bibliometric indicators and relevance evaluation behavior.

Keywords: relevance evaluation; academic search; citation counts; bibliometric indicators; information behavior

1 Introduction

Relevance is a core concept in information science that shapes how users and systems prioritize, filter and evaluate information (Greisdorf, 2000; Hjørland,

2000; Saracevic, 2016; White, 2017). Relevance is not a static concept, but a subjective and context-dependent process which encompasses many dimensions such as topicality, novelty or utility. Among those many factors that influence which information is perceived as relevant, popularity has emerged as a significant dimension especially for web search. Algorithms like Page-Rank exemplify how such measures can effectively aid in identifying relevant information. In contexts of scientific literature, a similar notion of popularity is embodied by citations. Citations are understood as a measure of recognition and influence of a research work within the scholarly community. Thus, they often serve as indicators of not only influence, but also quality. As such, citations and citation-based metrics, such as the journal impact factor, can influence publication practices, for example, in researchers' decisions on journal selection and editorial decisions on manuscript acceptance. Citation counts are included in many interfaces of academic search engines, such as Google Scholar, Web of Science or Scopus, and are mostly provided by the respective publisher on the article's web page. Yet, while the interplay of citations and relevance has been studied from the system's point of view, the role of citations for relevance evaluation behavior of users during academic literature search remains less understood.

2 Literature

Numerous studies have examined relevance clues – aspects impacting how users assess the relevance of documents (for an overview see Saracevic, 2016). Influential works by Barry and Schamber identified highly overlapping relevance criteria across various information environments, document types and user types, suggesting a common set of relevance criteria independent of users and information systems (Barry, 1994; Barry & Schamber, 1998; Schamber, 1991, 1994). However, Cool et al. (1993) highlighted that how users apply these common criteria varies depending on their specific context. More recent research stressed in particular the impact of domain knowledge on search behavior (Cole et al., 2011; Dinet et al., 2010; Sihvonen & Vakkari, 2004). While much of the literature focuses on relevance criteria, fewer studies address which document elements users consider to assess these criteria. Among the branch of literature on models and theory of relevance (for an overview see Mizzaro, 1998; Saracevic, 2007, 2016), exceptions include Wang and Soergel

(1998), who proposed a document selection model where document information elements like title, authors and journal are processed to judge relevance criteria such as topicality or quality. Behnert (2019) further refined this approach by differentiating between relevance properties (e.g., titles, abstracts) and relevance factors (e.g., time pressure, knowledge level), emphasizing how relevance factors influence weighting of relevance criteria.

In context of information retrieval, the relationship between bibliometric indicators and relevance has been studied from a system-oriented viewpoint, for example, on the theoretical basis of polyrepresentation (Breuer et al., 2022; Ingwersen, 1996; Skov et al., 2008) or relevance theory (White, 2007, 2011). Its role for relevance evaluation behavior of users has only recently gained attention. In a ranking experiment by Lemke et al. (2021) participants ranked publications regarding their expected relevance. The only information available to participants were six indicators (citations, journal impact factor, h-index, downloads, tweets, Mendeley readers). Findings suggest that researchers preferred the bibliometric indicators over usage metrics and altmetrics when deciding what to read. Conversely, Behnert (2022) reported inconclusive results when participants rated the usefulness of articles based on typical bibliographic information alongside three indicators (downloads, citations and cumulated citations of the author). Effects of high-value indicators were small and their direction unclear, albeit statistically significant. These contrasting findings suggest that additional relevance clues may dilute the influence of bibliometric indicators. This contribution aims to better understand how bibliometric indicators, particularly citations, influence relevance evaluation behavior. To this end, it is crucial to investigate their interaction with other relevance clues.

3 Method and Data

In this study, a within-subject experimental design was employed to examine how bibliometric indicators influence relevance evaluation behavior in academic searches. Each search engine results page (SERP) included either a citation count, an altmetric score or no indicator attached to the results. Participants performed searches for three scenarios, each presenting a different indicator. The SERP (see Fig. 1) featured ten articles with links to a detail page containing the abstract. The attached indicators were manipulated rather

than reflecting actual values. High-value indicators were strategically placed on the second, fifth, and seventh ranks to explore whether they influence the perceived relevance of the respective articles while accounting for ranking bias (those findings will be reported elsewhere).

Fig. 1 Search engine results page

The study was conducted online via Zoom. After a training scenario, participants performed three search scenarios (each with a different indicator provided) while sharing their screens and thinking aloud. Each scenario concluded once participants selected up to three documents from the SERP for reading. The scenarios were designed to address broad and accessible topics: ‘vegetarianism from a sociological perspective’, ‘attitudes of athletes towards doping’, and ‘use of big-data applications in health care’. A Graeco-Latin square design determined the order of scenarios and experimental conditions (i.e., indicators), resulting in 36 study configurations to which participants were randomly assigned.

A total of 50 participants from German research facilities were recruited via personal email invitation. The sample included 25 participants from medicine-related life sciences and 25 from social sciences, spanning all academic status groups (eleven predocs, 31 postdocs, eight professors), with 22 women and 28 men. Sessions, conducted in German or English between September and December 2020, averaged 90 minutes and were recorded and transcribed.

The analysis involved two coding steps using MaxQDA: First, participants’ interactions with the SERP were made analyzable by coding which results were mentioned, clicked, visited or selected for reading. Second, since previous research consistently found a common set of relevance criteria, the

relevance evaluation process was coded deductively, following the approach of qualitative content analysis (Mayring, 2000, 2022). The code system followed Behnert's (2019) relevance model, where users – affected by *relevance factors* – evaluate the relevance of an article with respect to *relevance criteria* by means of *relevance properties*. Codes were deduced from the relevance criteria reported in Barry (1994), Barry and Schamber (1998), Saračević (2016) and Wang and Soergel (1998). Criteria were merged and grouped according to their underlying concepts, and finally sorted into the threefold model of relevance criteria, factors and properties (Table 3). The properties *citations* and *altmetric score* were added.

Table 3: Relevance code system

Relevance criteria	Relevance factors	Relevance properties
<i>Topicality</i> topical match, topic, scope, depth, position	<i>Document collection</i> diversity	title abstract authors journal publication date language snippet full text search terms citations altmetric score
<i>Content</i> approach, data basis, findings, recency, clarity	<i>Prior knowledge</i> research culture, knowledge level, content novelty, document novelty, source novelty, understanding, mental effort	
<i>Scientific quality</i> quality, validity, accuracy, source reputation	<i>Affectiveness</i> personal credence, personal interest	
<i>Community</i> discipline, references, importance, impact	<i>Task</i> task constraints, time constraints, task difficulty	
<i>Access</i> accessibility, affordability	<i>System</i> rank, interface	

4 Results

Citations and altmetrics are considered relevance properties, i.e., they are document elements with which users draw conclusions about relevance criteria (e.g., importance within a field). In order to explore the usage of these bibliometric indicators during literature search, I firstly analyze the users'

overall interaction with the SERP and secondly focus on how citations relate to other relevance properties. Analyses of how citations relate to relevance criteria and factors, a comparison of citations and altmetrics as well as analyses on effects of manipulated high-value indicators (using the no-indicator condition as a baseline) will be reported elsewhere.

After reading the scenario description and clicking on the search icon, participants first of all intended to gain an overview of the whole SERP. This means they engaged primarily with the titles of search results and collected promising results in new tabs. Thereby they tended to engage with the whole SERP, i.e., almost all ten search results. After this first round of SERP inspection, the majority of participants performed only one more round. In this second round, they focused not only on the titles, but also other relevance properties (e.g., abstract, publication date, journal). They continued collecting results in new tabs that seemed potentially relevant. After this second round, they went on to assess the relevance of each collected result one by one, with a strong focus on the abstract. A smaller group of participants ($n = 17$) followed a different approach and went through the whole SERP more than two times. Each time, they focused on a different relevance property. For instance, they screened the titles in the first round, the journals in the second, the publication date in the third and citations in a last round. Subsequently they turned to the abstracts of results they opened beforehand and performed a final relevance assessment similar to the other participants. Citations were taken into consideration in both approaches by 44 participants (88%):

“At first, I take a look at the titles, actually. [...] Because the abstract only becomes important in the second step. One information of course catches my eye: And that is the number of citations.” (P21, par. 37–38, postdoc, sociology)

“So, I’m scanning through the titles and then I’m scanning through how many/so when they were published and how many citations they have so far.” (P33, par. 9, postdoc, neuroscience)

“Okay, so I simply look at the titles first, also the journal names, and also scan the citation rates a little bit. [...] And I also look at the years of publication.” (P39, par. 42, professor, sociology)

26 participants (52%) screened the SERP explicitly for highly cited articles:

“Yes, in this case, what catches my eye, is the second one, because it has many citations. You shouldn’t rely ONLY on that, but most of the time it is not bad.” (P10, par. 47, doctoral student, political science)

“However, and here comes a, I believe, a very important factor: this is a very, very, highly cited article. This means, as someone who doesn’t know anything

about the field, I would assume that this might be something important.” (P22, par. 42, postdoc, sociology)

“Then I would take a look at this one, only because it has been cited quite often.” (P31, par. 153, postdoc, sociology)

In this phase of the relevance evaluation process, when screening the SERP, participants were aiming at identifying relevant articles. In other words, their aim was to include articles in a set of possibly useful documents. In order to do so they made use of various relevance properties, focusing on finding topical matches, high-impact journals and highly cited works. Once a set of possibly relevant documents is created, participants’ focus shifted to mainly one relevance property, the abstract. In many cases, the abstracts were read thoroughly, applying relevance criteria especially regarding topic, content and quality. However, the relevance evaluation is not always straightforward and clear-cut. A participant may have read the title and abstract of an article, but is still in doubt of the paper’s relevance, for example, in terms of its topicality or the journal’s credibility. In this phase of the relevance evaluation process, citations come into play again – but the aim of using them has changed.

“This was only cited eight times, that is not really relevant then.” (P12, par. 165, postdoc, sociology)

“This doesn’t interest me that much, because/ it is a distribution study, but not as recent as the others and not so frequently cited.” (P27, par. 108, postdoc, political science)

“[The citations] play a certain role. Especially with older studies, I mean more sort of/ as an excluding factor, right? If I have an older study and it is POORLY cited, I would probably drop it.” (P7, par. 161, postdoc, sociology)

“I sort out texts which have like almost never been cited. [...] How many have cited something is kind of an exclusion criterion. If it’s only like one or two [...] I won’t even take a look at it. But if it’s a text that only FITS partly, but there were like 500 people citing it, then I am more likely to take look, of course.” (P25, par. 149, postdoc, science and technology studies)

In these examples, participants were not looking for highly cited articles. Their aim was no longer to *include*, but to *exclude*, to *sort out*. It becomes apparent how indicators can fulfill two main purposes: They can either be used as a *positive filter* early in the relevance evaluation process, or they can function as a *negative filter* at a later stage, typically after considering other relevance properties. I define a *positive filter* as users screening the SERP for high-value indicators, and a *negative filter* as excluding articles that are either poorly cited or not cited.

In both use cases, when screening for highly cited works and when sorting out poorly cited works, participants had a rather clear expectation of what should have received many or few citations. Hence, the manipulated indicators in this study caused irritation: For instance, if an article is perceived as rather narrow in scope, but has received many citations. Or if an article appeared in a high-impact journal, but was poorly cited. In such cases, participants were likely to draw conclusions about the quality of the respective article, either in one direction or the other.

“This is well cited, around 400 times, which I would say is good. In PNAS, which is a high-impact journal, I would say. Okay, then if I go for that paper, I’m expecting a LOT, if you ask me.” (P20, par. 16, postdoc, biophysics)

“So, it’s not cited so well. But it’s in SCIENCE so/ but if it didn’t get cites (laughs) in this time I think it wasn’t so appealing. [...] The recent one – oh this looks crazy. The most recent one got the most cites so that might be something special.” (P38, par. 55+181, doctoral student, biophysics)

“Well, ‘teenage vegetarianism’ is again very niche, but it’s well cited. No idea why.” (P9, par. 111, doctoral student, science and technology studies)

Further, these quotes illustrate that citations are interconnected with other relevance properties. Overall, participants mentioned citations 232 times. Hence, *citations* make 4.9% of all mentions of relevance properties (most mentions were made regarding *title* (1,809 mentions, 38.2%) and *abstract* (1,094 mentions, 23.1%)). Of these 232 mentions of *citations*, 71 (30.6%) included another relevance property. Table 4 shows the three relevance properties that were most often mentioned together with citations: *publication date*, *title* and *journal*. In these mentions, participants mainly considered them in order to facilitate the interpretation of citation counts.

Table 4: Co-occurrences of relevance properties with citations ($n = 232$)

code	co-occurrence with citations	co-occurrence with citations in %
publication date	30	12.9%
title	20	8.6%
journal	19	8.2%
no other relevance property	161	69.4%

Publication date is the property most often co-occurring with *citations* (12.9% of 232 *citation*-mentions). It was mostly used to determine the timeframe during which an article had the opportunity to accumulate citations:

“When you see this between the second and the sixth one, that are both from 2014, but the second one was cited almost three times as much. This is a hint that this could be more relevant.” (P1, par. 67, postdoc, neuroscience)

“Well, I would definitely look at that, as it performs quite well with 500 citations in those three years. I believe this is also a bit of an indicator, whether it is received in the community somehow.” (P12, par. 131, postdoc, sociology)

Title co-occurred second most often with *citations* (8.6%). It may contain information on the scope of an article, which points at the intended audience. Depending on the size of that audience, the number of people who could potentially cite an article is different.

“THIS focuses on global marine diversity, so it’s more specific, but still highly cited.” (P8, par. 95, doctoral student, sociology)

Thirdly, participants used the *journal* in 8.2% of all 232 *citation*-mentions similar to the *title*, as also the journal name may hint at the size of the community, regardless of participants not knowing most of the journals presented in this study:

“Well, the second was only/ maybe in a more specific journal [...], not cited as much. Which can also be related to that, right? That it’s simply less visible in that journal.” (P7, par. 174, postdoc, sociology)

In summary, participants showed a behavior of interpreting citations by means of other relevance properties. On the one hand, this may demonstrate that participants are aware that comparisons of citation rates should consider the context of the articles’ origin. On the other hand, it is striking how rare this interpreting behavior could be observed: Of all 232 mentions of citations, participants mentioned no other relevance property in 161 cases (69.4%, see Table 4). Here, participants most often simply stated the citation count, or that it was high or low, but they did not elaborate what this information may mean. This suggests that while participants sometimes consider contextual factors influencing citation rates, they may not always reflect on the significance of these elements in depth. Users of academic search engines may tend to focus on raw numbers without exploring their broader meaning or implications.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

This study investigated how citation counts are utilized during academic literature search. One limitation of this contribution lies in the artificial nature of the search setting inherent to controlled experimental designs. Additionally,

participants' domain knowledge was only limited, which implies limited knowledge of authors and journals in the field, which most likely impacted relevance decisions as suggested by Cole et al. (2011), Dinet et al. (2010) or Sihvonen and Vakkari (2004). However, the qualitative analysis focused to a lesser degree on the outcome of those decisions, but strongly on the relevance evaluation process leading to a relevance decision. Findings suggest a dual role for citations, functioning both as positive filters (to identify highly cited works) and negative filters (to exclude poorly cited works). Especially the latter invites further considerations, for example, in (interactive) information retrieval settings. Citations' dual role might also have contributed to the unclear direction of statistically significant results reported in Behnert (2022).

This study further found that some participants had rather clear expectations regarding citation patterns. These mainly resulted from contextualizing citation counts with other relevance properties, such as publication date, title and journal. However, this behavior of contextualizing indicators was only observed in few cases. Mostly, participants habitually relied on raw citation numbers without considering their broader context. This may lead to potentially oversimplified assessments of relevance. As a consequence, the interface design of current academic search engines may foster a behavior that contributes to the reinforcement of the Matthew effect and the narrowing of academic fields.

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